

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

D2.7: From LiDAR to tree architectural traits

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1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are target by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report is relevant for actors developing and improving tools and models that can support the second stakeholders' group. The extraction of relevant architectural traits from LiDAR scan data is useful for use in process-based models that have a simpler 3D implementation of trees (e.g., Hi-sAFe). These architectural traits can be used to design these simplified tree shapes. Furthermore, this extraction can be useful for calculation of tree parameters that can explain variation in tree-crop interactions across sites, which cannot be done, directly from the LiDAR data itself. This report contains a description of the procedure to extract relevant architectural features from a LiDAR scan data set, and presents the LiDAR data set that is available. In this respect we developed a script in the R programming language, and visualized the extracted features.

2 LiDAR

LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) is a remote sensing technology that uses laser light to measure distances and create highly detailed, three-dimensional maps of the environment. It works by sending laser pulses and measuring the time it takes for them to return after bouncing off objects, allowing for accurate mapping of terrain and objects. LiDAR is commonly used in applications such as autonomous vehicles, forestry, urban planning, and archaeology to capture precise spatial information. Its ability to provide detailed and accurate data makes it valuable for various industries and applications. In the context of agroforestry, LiDAR data can provide architectural traits of trees and tree rows in the field.

3 From point clouds to QSMs

Point clouds are the first result of a LiDAR scan (Figure 1). They represent the position of detected objects in the three dimensional space. The higher the resolution, the more points the LiDAR scan will generate.

Figure 1: Example of a point cloud generated by LiDAR (De Waele 2023).

These point clouds can then be processed into Quantitative Structure Models (QSMs) using the MatLab package [TreeQSM](#). In a QSM, the points are merged into a hierarchical collection of cylinders, representing the tree trunk and branches of different orders (Figure 2). These cylinders allow to estimate topological, geometrical and volumetric metrics of the woody structure of the tree.

Figure 2: Example of a quantitative structure model of an individual tree (De Waele 2023).

4 From QSMs to architectural traits

Using the R package ITSM_e (Terry_n 2023), relevant architectural traits can be extracted from QSMs. The package can be installed and loaded as follows:

```
if(!require("devtools")) install.packages("devtools")
if(!require("ITSMe")) devtools::install_github("lmterryn/ITSMe",
build_vignettes = TRUE)
if(!require("tidyverse")) install.packages("tidyverse")
```

We also use the tidyverse package for this extraction.

A QSM file, generated by the TreeQSM package in MatLab, can be imported in R as follows:

```
Tree_1 <- "path/to/tree.qsm"
qsm_1 <- ITSMe::read_tree_qsm(Tree_1)
```

Each QSM file can contain multiple QSMs, as exported by the TreeQSM package from MatLab. Typically, there are different settings, with which the QSM is built from the point cloud, and multiple QSMs from the same point cloud can be generated.

We developed an R function that:

- lists all the QSM files in a folder
- reads each QSM file using ITSM_e::read_tree_qsm

- lists all the QSMs, made by the MatLab TreeQSM package, in the qsm file
- extracts the interesting architectural features
- writes these features in a dataframe (or tibble)

The function `extract_qsm` extracts the relevant traits from a QSM read into R. The `read_and_extract` function uses the `ITSM::read_tree_qsm` function to read a QSM file into R, and then calls the function `extract_qsm`.

```
if(!require("tidyverse")) install.packages("tidyverse")
library("ITSM")

extract_qsm <- function(qsm){
  return(tibble(Diameter_BH = dbh_qsm(treedata = qsm$treedata),
    Height_Tree = tree_height_qsm(treedata = qsm$treedata),
    Height_Trunk = trunk_height_qsm(treedata = qsm$treedata),
    Height_Crown_start = crown_start_height_qsm(treedata =
qsm$treedata,
                                                    cylinder =
qsm$cylinder),
    Height_Crown = crown_height_qsm(treedata = qsm$treedata,
                                     cylinder = qsm$cylinder),
    DiamHeight_Crown=crown_diameterheight_ratio_qsm(treedata=qsm$treedata,
                                                    cylinder =
qsm$cylinder)
  ))
}

read_and_extract <- function(qsmfile){
  print(basename(qsmfile))
  return(ITSM::read_tree_qsm(qsmfile) %>%
    map(extract_qsm) %>%
    list_rbind() %>%
    mutate(qsm = 1:nrow(.),
           qsm_file = basename(qsmfile)))
}
```

5 Belgian data set

In the framework of multiple agroforestry-related projects (VLAIO Agroforestry2025, PDPO Carbon Farming, DigitAF) and the master thesis of Robbe De Waele (De Waele 2023), LiDAR scans were made from different hedges in the vicinity of Melle, Belgium.

Table 1: Location of the hedges, scanned by LiDAR

Location ID	Latitude	Longitude
Assel	50.949	3.753
Bos	50.962	3.721
Hundel	50.959	3.739
Kasteel	50.959	3.808
Makke	50.948	3.722
Meer	50.976	3.791

Location ID	Latitude	Longitude
Poel	50.980	3.755
Vierhoek	50.972	3.808
Wulgen	50.962	3.811
Zonne	50.969	3.779

From these scans, individual trees were separated for QSM building. In total, a data set of 85 trees is available including the following species:

- *Carpinus betulus*
- *Corylus avellana*
- *Quercus robur*
- *Quercus rubra*
- *Salix alba*

Below, we listed the filenames of the available data:

```
[1] "Assel_B_001_qsm.mat" "Assel_B_002_qsm.mat" "Assel_B_004_qsm.mat"
[4] "Assel_B_005_qsm.mat" "Assel_B_006_qsm.mat"
"Assel_O_001_qsm.mat"[7] "Assel_O_002_qsm.mat" "Assel_O_003_qsm.mat"
"Assel_S_001_qsm.mat"
[10] "Assel_S_002_qsm.mat" "Assel_S_003_qsm.mat" "Bos_C_001_qsm.mat"
[13] "Bos_C_002_qsm.mat" "Bos_C_003_qsm.mat" "Bos_C_004_qsm.mat"
[16] "Bos_C_005_qsm.mat" "Hundel_F_001_qsm.mat" "Hundel_Q_001_qsm.mat"
[19] "Hundel_Q_002_qsm.mat" "Hundel_Q_003_qsm.mat" "Hundel_Q_004_qsm.mat"
[22] "Hundel_Q_005_qsm.mat" "Hundel_Q_006_qsm.mat" "Kasteel_C_001_qsm.mat"
[25] "Kasteel_C_002_qsm.mat" "Kasteel_C_003_qsm.mat"
"Kasteel_C_004_qsm.mat"
[28] "Kasteel_F_001_qsm.mat" "Kasteel_F_002_qsm.mat"
"Kasteel_P_001_qsm.mat"
[31] "Kasteel_P_002_qsm.mat" "Kasteel_P_003_qsm.mat"
"Kasteel_P_004_qsm.mat"
[34] "Kasteel_P_005_qsm.mat" "Kasteel_P_006_qsm.mat"
"Makke_C_001_qsm.mat"
[37] "Makke_C_002_qsm.mat" "Makke_C_003_qsm.mat"
"Makke_C_004_qsm.mat"
[40] "Makke_C_005_qsm.mat" "Makke_C_006_qsm.mat"
"Meer_C_001_qsm.mat"
[43] "Meer_C_002_qsm.mat" "Meer_C_003_qsm.mat"
"Meer_C_004_qsm.mat"
[46] "Meer_C_006_qsm.mat" "Meer_Q_001_qsm.mat"
"Meer_Q_002_qsm.mat"
[49] "Meer_Q_003_qsm.mat" "Meer_S_002_qsm.mat"
"Meer_S_008_qsm.mat"
[52] "Poel_F_001_qsm.mat" "Poel_Q_001_qsm.mat"
"Poel_Q_002_qsm.mat"
[55] "Poel_Q_003_qsm.mat" "Poel_Q_004_qsm.mat"
"Poel_Q_005_qsm.mat"
[58] "Poel_Q_006_qsm.mat" "Poel_Q_007_qsm.mat"
"Poel_Q_008_qsm.mat"
[61] "Vierhoek_A_001_qsm.mat" "Vierhoek_A_002_qsm.mat"
"Vierhoek_A_005_qsm.mat"
[64] "Vierhoek_A_006_qsm.mat" "Vierhoek_A_007_qsm.mat"
"Vierhoek_O_001_qsm.mat"
[67] "Vierhoek_O_002_qsm.mat" "Vierhoek_Q_001_qsm.mat"
```

```

"Vierhoek_S_001_qsm.mat"
[70] "Vierhoek_S_002_qsm.mat" "Vierhoek_S_003_qsm.mat"
"Vierhoek_S_005_qsm.mat"
[73] "Vierhoek_V_001_qsm.mat" "Wulg_S_001_qsm.mat"
"Wulg_S_002_qsm.mat"
[76] "Wulg_S_003_qsm.mat"      "Wulg_S_004_qsm.mat"
"Wulg_S_005_qsm.mat"
[79] "Wulg_S_006_qsm.mat"      "Wulg_S_007_qsm.mat"
"Wulg_S_008_qsm.mat"
[82] "Zonne_A_001_qsm.mat"     "Zonne_A_002_qsm.mat"
"Zonne_A_003_qsm.mat"
[85] "Zonne_P_001_qsm.mat"

```

We extract the traits from all QSM files using the `purrr::map` function (for 85 QSMs, it takes about 2 hr):

```

All_qsm_traits <- list.files(path = path, full.names = T) %>%
  map(read_and_extract) %>%
  list_rbind()

```

The dataframe (or tibble) `All_qsm_traits` now contains traits from all QSMs, including the different versions per tree.

6 Data visualisation

For data visualisation, we will give an `id` (from 1 to 85) to the `qsm_file` variable.

6.1 Tree height

The boxplots show the variation of the different QSMs (n=10) per tree.

Figure 3: Extracted tree height from the 85 QSM files. Each QSM file contained multiple versions, calculated from the same point cloud using TeeQSM.

6.2 Trunk height

Figure 4: Extracted trunk height from the 85 QSM files. Each QSM file contained multiple versions, calculated from the same point cloud using TeeQSM.

6.3 Crown height

Figure 5: Extracted crown height from the 85 QSM files. Each QSM file contained multiple versions, calculated from the same point cloud using TeeQSM.

6.4 Crown Diameter-to-Height ratio

Figure 6: Extracted crown diameter-to-height ratio from the 85 QSM files. Each QSM file contained multiple versions, calculated from the same point cloud using TeeQSM.

6.5 Other relevant traits

Extraction of other potentially relevant architectural traits (e.g., crown Volume or crown Envelope), is currently not possible using the ITSM package. It will be investigated if extraction of these traits could be added to the toolbox.

7 Data set from Restinclières, France.

The data set from Restinclières, France (43.722 °N, 4.038 °W) contains scans of 150 trees and was captured in 2021 (figure 7).

Figure 7: point cloud of a tree row in Restinclières agroforestry platform

The point cloud was then divided to isolated individual trees (figure 8, left). From this data, tree characteristics were extracted such as canopy volume (figure 8, right) and tree height. For a sample of trees, coarse roots were carefully dug out and scanned, to digitalize the root architecture (figure 8, left).

Figure 8: isolated tree captured from LiDAR point cloud, and visualisation of canopy volume.

8 Conclusion

Our workflow using R and the package ITSMe (Terry 2023), enables relatively easy extraction of tree architectural traits from QSM data like tree height, trunk height, crown height and crown diameter-to-height ratio. Extension of this toolbox to extract other potentially relevant traits (e.g., crown volume, or crown envelope) will be investigated. The extraction of architectural traits is required to interpret tree-crop interaction effects as this cannot be done directly from the point cloud or the QSM. Furthermore, derived architectural traits can be used to parameterise or validate 3D biophysical models such as Hi-sAFe.

9 Acknowledgements

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10 References

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